

New species of the genus *Mesosa* Latreille, 1829 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from North Iran

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Abstract: *Mesosa (Aplocnemia) jarzabekae* sp. n. close to *M. (A.) obscuricornis* Pic, 1894 is described from North Iran (Mazandaran). The main distinguishing character is the absence of erect elytral setae.

The subgenus *Aplocnemia* Stephens, 1831 of the genus *Mesosa* Latreille, 1829 was known up to now in Caucasus and neighbor areas of Iran and Turkey being represented by two closely related species: *M. (A.) nebulosa* (Fabricius, 1781) - widely distributed in the West Palaearctics and *M. (A.) obscuricornis* Pic, 1894 - an endemic species of Azerbaijanian Talysh Area and West Elburs Ridge in Iran (Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010). A discovery of a third species in Mazandaran is very interesting, but not that surprising. There are several vicariant species or subspecies replacing Talysh taxa in North Iran. *Cerambyx elbursi* Jureček, 1924 replaces *C. multiplicatus* Motschulsky, 1860; *Isotomus comptus gilanus* (Pic, 1911) replaces *I. comptus comptus* (Mannerheim, 1825) which is very numerous in Talysh Area and so on.

Mesosa (Aplocnemia) jarzabekae sp. n.

Fig. 1

Type locality. North Iran, Mazandaran, Sari-Dodangeh-Boola Forest, 10 km s Part Kola, 995 m, 36.046713°N, 53.290651°E

Two males were collected with flight interception traps in the downed tree crown of a broken *Carpinus betulus*. However, only holotype is in good condition. The second male lost a part of elytral pubescence, and as a result its elytral design is indistinct. The holotype is described below. The new species is close to *M. (A.) obscuricornis* Pic, 1894 (Fig. 2).

Body relatively big, elongated; cuticle black; ground recumbent elytral and pronotal pubescence brown; erect elytral and pronotal setae absent; (erect elytral and pronotal setae present in *M. obscuricornis* and distributed just to elytral apex); a few small granules hardly pronounced near elytral bases (as well as in *M. obscuricornis*); vertex and pronotum with groups of regular dots, without wrinkles or granules; sculpture of 1st antennal joint is very fine, with several distinct dots; cicatrix not complete, but distinct; antennae much longer than body, surpassing elytral apex by 5 apical joints, with numerous erect setae, which are relatively shorter than in *M. obscuricornis*; 1st antennal joint about as long as 5th; 4th joint is much longer than 5th, and 3rd joint is the longest; prothorax about 1.3 times shorter than its basal width; pronotal sculpture is similar to *M. obscuricornis* but dots are definitely smaller; all pronotal setae are brown, while in *M. obscuricornis* white pronotal setae are rather numerous; scutellum strongly transverse and distinctly emarginated, while in *M. obscuricornis* scutellum subquadrate; elytra about 2 times longer than its basal width, while in *M. obscuricornis* elytra a little shorter - about 1.9 times longer than wide; elytral punctation is smaller, less regular than in *M. obscuricornis* and much sparser; the size of neighbor elytral dots can be rather different; black rings surrounding dots hardly pronounced; central elytral band strongly bordered with black stripes (never so distinct in *M. obscuricornis*), internal margins of black stripes bordered with white setae much more numerous anteriorly; erect setae of legs shorter; abdomen pubescence sparser, rather pale, nearly white; 2nd - 4th visible abdominal sternites with elongated transverse areas of very dense

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short pubescence typical for the subgenus; in *M. obscuricornis* and *M. nebulosa* these areas are about as dark-brown as surrounding abdominal pubescence, while in the new species the areas are nearly white; last abdominal tergites and sternites rounded; postpygidium a little angulated; body length: 10.8-14.4 mm, width: 4.0-5.1 mm.

Remark. *Mesosa (Aplocnemia) jarzabekae* sp. n. is close to *M. obscuricornis*, but differs by many small characters. The most significant character seems to be the absence of erect elytral setae.

Materials. Holotype, male with label: "North Iran, Mazandaran, Sari-Dodangeh-Boola Forest, 10km s Part Kola, 995 m, 36.046713°N, 53.290651°E, *Carpinus* trap 4-3, 7.2015, leg. H.Barimani" - collection of M.Danilevsky; paratype, male, with the label: "North Iran, Mazandaran, Sari-Dodangeh-Boola Forest, 10km s Part Kola, 995m, 36.046713°N, 53.290651°E, *Carpinus* trap 4-2, 6.2015, leg. H.Barimani" - collection of J. Müller.

M. obscuricornis: 4 males and 3 females collected near Avrora village in Girkan Natural Reserve (1972, 1980-1981, 1984) by M.Danilevsky - collection of M.Danilevsky.

M. nebulosa: 4 males and 7 females from West Europe, Caucasus and North Africa - collection of M.Danilevsky.

Dedication. The new species is dedicated to Andrea Jarzabek-Müller - wife of Dr. Müller, who is hunting with him beetles all over Palaearctic Region.

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Fig. 1. Holotype, male, *Mesosa (Aplocnemia) jarzabekae* sp. n.:

Fig. 2. *Mesosa (Aplocnemia) obscuricornis*, male, Azerbaijan, Talysh Area [about 38.656085°N, 48.798577°E], Avrora village, 24.7.1972, M. Danilevsky leg.

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